

Co-designing the OSNL Programme 2026-2027

Citizen Science/ societal engagement

Frederike Schmitz | Citizen Science NL networking day

14th January 2025

Mission of Open Science NL

To advance and accelerate
open science in the Netherlands
with the goal of **making
open science the norm**

By providing (temporary) **funding** for projects, initiatives and infrastructures, 2 year work programmes

By **monitoring** and evaluating progress

By providing a forum for **exchange** of best practice

By organising and facilitating **coordination** at a national level

The 2024/2025 work programme

National Programme Open Science provided overall framework

Approved by the Steering Board & based on community consultation at various levels

A diverse array of instruments, tailored to specific topics and community needs

24/25 Programme

Citizen Science/ societal engagement support

National Citizen Science network (CS-NL)

Goal

- Facilitating the connection of citizen science and societal engagement experts (within and outside of academia)

What?

- € 1.1 million for 4 years, Targeted grant for CS-NL

Innovative citizen science calls

Goal

- Design funding schemes which address challenges & bottlenecks for non-academic contributions (citizens)

What?

- Pre-call trajectory at NWO (OS-NL & NWA)
- Goal: designated call in 2025 (expected)

Capacity building

Goal

- Creation of hubs with expertise in Citizen Science/ societal engagement at research organisations (supporting others)

What?

- € 2 million, 4 years competitive call

Infrastructure

Goal

- Supporting open science (digital) infrastructure (broad scope incl. Citizen Science/ societal engagement)

What?

- € 17.5 million, competitive call

Challenges and priorities signalled by the community

Dec 2022

NPOS lists challenges as part of the community consultations

October 2024

Open Science festival participants have gathered and discussed challenges and possible solutions

[Openscience.nl/blogposts](https://www.openscience.nl/blogposts)

June/Dec 2024

Advisory board collected and discussed collected challenges from the festival

<https://www.openscience.nl/en/advisory-panels>

Q1/2 of 2025

Community feedback;
Events & online

Challenges collected by the Advisory panel

- **Support of Citizen Science outside of academia:** e.g. in form of grassroots initiatives (also as a form of democratisation/empowerment vs commercial drive).
- **Oversight & monitoring** of engagement & citizen science and linking this to impact.
- **Recognition** of citizens (in form of (financial) compensation, training/learning etc.) and researchers (career paths etc.).
- **Long-term nature of impact** versus short-term model of funding and support for citizen science.
- **Uptake of citizen-gathered insights & data in policy making.** How can data and insights from citizen science projects be more embedded in policymaking?
- **Knowledge exchange/ professionalization:** Citizen engagement throughout the whole research cycle & receiving professional support in higher education (quality debate), including training needs: defining and delivering essential skills for citizen science and societal engagement.

Challenges collected by the Advisory panel

- **Increasing diversity & inclusion and meaningfully engage with participants:** How do we ensure that diverse groups, domains, and associations are included and that we engage them meaningfully?
- **Barriers to Communication:** There are significant obstacles to accessing and understanding scientific information due to technical jargon and often limited trust in institutions is an additional hindrance.
- **Building (Open Knowledge) Infrastructures** that facilitate engagement: Questions of data safety, privacy, and accessibility often remain unresolved in citizen science projects.
- **Ethics in Citizen Science and engagement** (process & relationship-wise).
- **Bridging Stakeholders and Professional Support:** Stronger connections are needed between science, policy, and citizens to ensure collaborative progress.
- **Citizen Science is embedded** in diverse disciplines (e.g. social sciences).
- **Reforming Science Culture:** How can societal engagement / citizen science become an integral part of research, and how do we overcome resistance to this shift?

Potential interventions collected by the Advisory panel

- Focus on capacity building in the next work programme: propose training programmes, train-the-trainer, mentorship programmes etc.
- The idea about an accessibility fund was raised. This could be used for compensation. Why and how would we want to use such a fund?
- The community could work on guidelines when engaging non-researchers. These could be provided to all NWO applicants when including engagement elements. Part of these guidelines could be reference to literature about compensation (what is known..) or best practices but also pointing to (possible) negative effects (see discussions around impact & [recognition of negative impact](#)). Reference documents: The UK the National Institute for Health & Care Research has quite [detailed guidelines on payment of public contributors](#).

What do you think?

12:00-12:10 [10 min]

Is there anything missing?

Individually write post-its for missing challenges

12:10-12:20 [10 min]

Brainstorm about possible solutions

Choose 3 items for which you propose interventions (post- it's)

12:20-12:35 [15 min]

Open Science NL/NWO's toolbox

1 Programme outcome/impact

Recap & next steps

Thank you for your ideas and feedback

- Input new work programme: *until spring 2025* (community, advisory panel)
- Translation challenges into (financial) instruments & action points
- Feedback on draft version of new work programme: *spring/summer 2025* (online event?)
- **Autumn 2025 Steering board** discusses & **decides on new work programme**

Do you have any questions?

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